

What is a Heritage Community?

The concept of Heritage Community stems from the **Faro Convention** (Framework Convention of the Council of Europe on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society, signed in Faro in 2005), and is a key concept that defines **the relationship between people and cultural heritage**. The convention defines them in Article 2.b

A **'heritage community'** refers to a group of people who value specific aspects of cultural heritage that they wish to preserve and pass on to future generations within the framework of public action.

How to carry it out?

The following steps should be taken:

- 1 Initial meeting with those potentially interested in joining the heritage community
- 2 Preparation of proposals for each case: led by active agents within the heritage community- what cultural heritage item, traditions, and local products can be used as a mechanism for sustainable tourism with and for the community?
- 3 Drafting of an annex document with a commitment to hold an annual meeting and a dissemination activity

Get involved!

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Towards the Creation of a Heritage Community

Heritage unites us,
community strengthens us.

What is it for?

- Encourage **participation and cooperation**
- **Keep heritage** and its associated practices alive
- Designing common strategies for **sustainable development**
- **Recognising and valuing** what people consider significant
- **Avoiding mass tourism** and loss of identity
- Act as a **mechanism for redistributing services** and benefits
- Strengthening the **sense of belonging** and collective identity

Who is it aimed at?

- **Local community:**
neighbors, families, farmers, irrigators....
- **Associations and groups:**
women's associations, cultural associations, local foundations, etc
- **Experts and professionals:**
historians, archaeologists, tour guides, local businesses, teachers, etc
- **Public institutions:**
town councils, provincial councils
- **Educational community:**
schools, colleges, training centres...

What can be done?

- 1 Assess and include the agricultural heritage and local products of local environs
- 2 Agreements on remuneration for ecosystem services
- 3 Agreements between entities for educational and cultural collaboration
- 4 Specific training activities on the heritage diversity of each municipality
- 5 Activities (such as fairs, competitions, conferences, crowdsourced surveys, publications) in support of local heritage that allow for the dissemination of heritage awareness